

Experimental verification of statistical correlation between FRP elastic properties by VFM and DIC

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Outlines

1. Background and objective
2. Specimen configuration optimization
3. Experimental verification of correlation coefficients
4. Conclusions

1. Background and objective

- FRP shows great uncertainty on its mechanical properties.
- The uncertainty needs to be carefully considered to evaluation accurate structure reliability.

Uncertainty of mechanical properties of T300/epoxy – by experiments

Basic design variables	Mean values	Coefficient of variance, (COV)
E_{11}	133.92 GPa	0.04618
E_{22}	8.84 GPa	0.03959
G_{12}	4.45 GPa	0.03146
ν_{12}	0.336	0.05952
X_t	1787 MPa	0.14270
X_c	1185 MPa	0.13502
Y_t	58.36 MPa	0.11138
Y_c	249.96 MPa	0.07437
R	92.60 MPa	0.04125
S	106.93 MPa	0.02434

1. Background and objective

- Uncertainty of lamina mechanical properties could also be estimated from constituent material uncertainty.

$$E_{11} = V_f E_{f11} + V_m E_m$$

$$E_{22} = \frac{(V_f + V_m a_{11})(V_f + V_m a_{22})}{\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (V_f + V_m a_{11})(V_f S_{f22} + a_{22} V_m S_{m22}) \\ + V_f V_m (S_{m12} - S_{f12}) a_{12} \end{array} \right\}}$$

$$\nu_{12} = V_f \nu_{f11} + V_m \nu_m$$

$$G_{12} = \frac{(G_{f12} + G_m) + V_f (G_{f12} - G_m)}{(G_{f12} + G_m) - V_f (G_{f12} - G_m)}$$

Table 1. Statistics of the micro-scale random variables.²⁰

Random variable	Mean	COV	Distribution type
<i>Fiber</i>			
Normal modulus, E_{f11}	213.7 (GPa)	5.9% ⁴⁰	Normal
Normal modulus, E_{f22}	13.8 (GPa)	12% ⁴¹	Normal
Shear modulus, G_{f12}	13.8 (GPa)	5.0% ⁴²	Normal
Poisson's ratio, ν_{f12}	0.2	5.0%	Normal
Tensile strength, σ_{fu}	2.25 (GPa)	15% ⁴⁰	Weibull ^a
<i>Matrix</i>			
Young's modulus, E_m	3.45 (GPa)	2.5% ⁴³	Normal
Poisson's ratio, ν_m	0.35	5.0%	Normal
Tangent modulus, E_{mT}	0.38 (GPa)	4.0%	Normal
Ultimate normal strength, σ_{mu}	34.6 (MPa)	4.0% ⁴⁴	Weibull ^b
Yield normal strength, σ_{my}	19.6 (MPa)	4.0%	Weibull ^c
Ultimate shear strength, τ_{mu}	69.2 (MPa)	3.6% ⁴⁴	Weibull ^d
<i>Fabrication</i>			
FVR, V_f	0.66	5.0% ³⁹	Normal

1. Background and objective

- Uncertainty of lamina mechanical properties could also be estimated from constituent material uncertainty.

Fig. 3. Geometrical shape and mesh of the FE modeling.

Table 2
Statistics of mechanical properties of fibre and matrix.

	Mean value	Standard deviation	Distribution type
<i>E-glass fibre</i>			
E	72 GPa	3.6 GPa	Normal
ν	0.2	0.04	Normal
<i>Carbon fibre</i>			
E_1	213.7 GPa	12.6 GPa	Normal
E_2	13.8 GPa	1.65 GPa	Normal
ν_{12}	0.2	0.01	Normal
G_{12}	13.8 GPa	0.69 GPa	Normal
ν_{23}	0.3	0.015	Normal
<i>Epoxy</i>			
E	3.45	0.086 GPa	Normal
ν	0.35	0.0175	Normal
V_f^\dagger	0.75	0.038	Normal

1. Background and objective

- Uncertainty of lamina mechanical properties could also be estimated from constituent material uncertainty.

Table 2. The statistics of unidirectional AS/3501-5.

Random variables	Linear correlation coefficient						Mean	Cov	Distribution
	E_{11}	E_{22}	ν_{12}	G_{12}	X_T	Y_T			
E_{11} (GPa)	1						142.21	0.076	Normal
E_{22} (GPa)	0.342	1					8.52	0.078	Normal
ν_{12}	-0.303	-0.208	1				0.251	0.041	Normal
G_{12} (GPa)	0.599	0.539	-0.52	1			4.40	0.083	Normal

- ◆ Significant statistical correlation between lamina mechanical properties is observed.
- ◆ The statistical correlation is not observed from experimental work using ASTM or ISO test methods, as each test configuration only provides one modulus.

1. Background and objective

- Our recent study demonstrated that the statistical correlation between lamina elastic properties would greatly affect composite structure reliability, which is often ignored in many studies.

1. Background and objective

- Still, the statistical correlation between lamina elastic properties **is still limited to theoretical prediction, and it has not been experimentally verified**, to the best of our knowledge.
- A combination of VFM and DIC would possibly provides a good approach for the experimental verification.

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2. Test configuration optimization

- UD CFRP with a circular hole is employed as specimen, and tensile load is applied.
- DIC is used to characterize heterogeneous deformation, and VFM is used to derive E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} , ν_{12} .
- Fibre orientation (θ) and hole diameter (ϕ) are to be optimized so that the derived elastic properties are least sensitive to strain measurement error.

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2. Test configuration optimization

- FE model is constructed to derive strain field.

2. Test configuration optimization

- An random strain noise field of $N(0, 1 \times 10^{-4})$ is added to strain field derived by FE. 10^4 Monte-Carlo simulation is carried out, and an error function β is defined.

$$\beta = \frac{1}{4} \sum_i \left(\frac{|\Delta_i - \Delta_{i-ref}|}{\Delta_{i-ref}} \right)$$

$r=3.5\text{mm}$ and $\theta=90^\circ$, provides the best prediction!

3. Experimental verification

➤ Experiment set-up

3D-DIC set-up

Technique used	Image correlation
Subset size	31×31 pixels ²
Shift	5 pixels
Camera	8 bit, Vic 5M
Field of view	35mm \times 40mm
Spatial resolution	0.0285 mm/pixel
Displacement resolution	around 0.025 pixel
Strain resolution	around 0.8×10^{-4}

3. Experimental verification

- Typical strain field measured by DIC at $F = 9\text{kN}$. The strain field agrees well with FE modeling.

Force history

a) ϵ_x ; b) ϵ_y ; c) γ_{xy}

3. Experimental verification

- Virtual Field Method is employed to derive E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} and ν_{12} .

$$\text{Quasi-static: } - \int_V \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} T_i u_i^* dS = 0$$

For 2D, linear elasticity, orthotropic, fiber coordinate system:

$$Q_{11} \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_1^* + Q_{22} \varepsilon_2 \varepsilon_2^* + Q_{12} (\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2^* + \varepsilon_2 \varepsilon_1^*) + Q_{66} \varepsilon_6 \varepsilon_6^* = F/t$$

Four independent VFs should be defined.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} U_x^*|_{y=L} = 0 \\ U_{x,y}^*|_{y=0} = 0 \\ U_y^*|_{y=L} = \text{constant} \end{array} \right.$$

3. Experimental verification

- Experimental measurement on the correlation coefficients between lamina elastic properties generally agrees well with theoretical prediction.
- The correlation coefficients between ν_{12} and other elastic properties is negative, while the correlation coefficients between E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} are positive.
- Significant and positive correlation exists between E_{22} and G_{12} .

Random variables	Linear correlation coefficient				Mean	CV	Ref
	E_{11}	E_{22}	ν_{12}	G_{12}			
E_{11} (GPa)	1				135.1	0.043	133.9
E_{22} (GPa)	0.28/0.54*	1			7.50	0.145	8.84
ν_{12}	-0.10/-0.35*	-0.56/-0.30*	1		0.33	0.049	0.34
G_{12} (GPa)	0.31/0.63*	0.87/0.84*	-0.76/-0.50*	1	3.65	0.156	4.45

*: values by theoretical prediction in our previous work.

4. Conclusions

- An experimental approach is proposed to determine the statistical correlation between lamina elastic properties of CFRP, by a combination of DIC and VFM.
- The experimental results on linear correlation between lamina elastic properties agree well with theoretical prediction.
- The statistical correlation between lamina elastic properties of CFRP can not experimentally verified by conventional test methods suggested by ASTM or ISO test standards, hence this maybe another great application for VFM.

A 3D-rendered whiteboard on a stand. The whiteboard is white and has the word "Thanks!" written on it in a blue, bold, sans-serif font. The stand is grey and has four red clips on each side. The whiteboard is mounted on a grey frame with two horizontal bars. The stand has two legs, each with a triangular base. A shadow is cast on the ground below the whiteboard.

Thanks!